

ADOLESCENTS' LONELINESS, SURVIVAL, AND COPING SKILLS: A GENDER PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

The current study was designed to examine the relevance of strategies used for coping with loneliness. 100 School students (50 boys, 50 girls) and 100 college students (50 boys, 50 girls) completed the revised UCLA loneliness scale by Russell Peplau and Cutrona, 1980 and were asked to provide information regarding demographic data. The study revealed important findings: A) female adolescents are significantly lonelier than male adolescents, B) Females scored higher on loneliness during early adolescence and males experienced higher loneliness during late adolescence, C) demographic variables fail to relate to the experience of loneliness, and D) the majority of adolescents regardless of age and sex reported the use of solitary involvement for coping with loneliness. Although various activities and events were mentioned for dealing with loneliness, they were clearly not in the context of increasing the number of social contexts for developing existing relationships into ones of greater depth. The activities engaged in were not geared towards masking the pain, suppressing cognitive processes, or avoiding the experience altogether. On the contrary, they allowed the person time to adjust to loneliness and to decide to face it courageously while not becoming immobilized in the process. It was also found that the adolescents did not mention any coping strategies referring to reflective solitude, involving restructuring loneliness into solitude by cognitively changing their perception of the situation.

Keywords: loneliness, solitude, coping skills, surviving skills, adolescents, late and middle adolescents.

Introduction:

A key part of human development and well-being is the need to belong and to feel socially linked. But when it is not fulfilled, it brings loneliness. There are numerous definitions of loneliness. "A condition of solitude or being alone" is a popular definition. The alternative definition reads, "Loneliness is not always associated with solitude." It is instead "a state of mind" and "the perception of being alone and isolated that matters most." (Tiwari, 2013). Despite being a common human emotion, loneliness is a complex and individual experience for each person. According to research (Cacioppo & Cacioppo, 2018), depression, introversion, poor social skills, and social isolation are all linked to loneliness. Because it lacks a single common cause, there are wide variations in both prevention and therapy for this harmful mental state.

An unpleasant emotional reaction to feeling alone is loneliness. Social pain, a psychological process that drives people to seek out social connections, is another term for loneliness. It frequently evokes undesired lack of closeness and connection. While most definitions of loneliness refer to a feeling of being alone or alone in the world, loneliness is actually a mental state. People who are lonely experience empty, lonely, and unwelcome feelings. People who are lonely frequently want for human interaction, yet their mental state makes making friends more challenging. Many experts agree that loneliness is not always associated with being alone. Instead, loneliness affects your state of mind when you feel isolated and alone.

Adolescence is a crucial period for understanding the effects of loneliness since young people are going through a variety of developmental transitions, both biological and social, such as the start of puberty and the transfer from elementary to secondary school. Adolescence is when loneliness is most common, with more than 70 percent of adolescents consistently feeling lonely at age 18. (Goosby et al., 2013) Adolescents are also switching from their parents to their peers as their key socializing agents during this developmental period (Crosnoe 2000). Such a variety of changes can cause emotional turmoil and

friendship instability, which over time may have a negative impact on one's mental and physical health. Particularly for adolescents, parental support and school connection may serve as important coping factors for physical and mental health during a developmental stage when distress is prevalent (Resnick et al., 1997; Giordano, 2003). Social connections matter for long-term health (Umberson and Montez 2010). According to statistics, loneliness is on the rise, especially among younger generations. One 2019 poll found that 22% of adults between the years of 18 and 27 admitted experiencing no friends at all, while 25% said they had no close friends (Ballard, 2019). Ironically, social media's popularity and the growth of the internet are also partly to blame. After 2012, the psychological health of teenagers all across the world began to deteriorate in tandem with the spread of smartphones and greater internet usage, while causality cannot be established. School loneliness is positively connected with negative affect and inversely correlated with positive affect and life satisfaction. (Twenge et al., 2021)

Although it has gained popularity among young people, loneliness is not a recent phenomenon. According to earlier research by Peplau and Perlman, loneliness is comprised of three primary characteristics: it is a personal experience, a distasteful and upsetting mood, and it is a result of a lack of human relationships. Loneliness is "a social discomfort caused by a perceived deficit in the quantity or quality of an individual's social connection," according to a recent systematic review (Osborn, Weatherburn, and French, 2020). These definitions from the past and present shed light on the quantity and quality of intimate social connections as well as unpleasant and traumatic events. Teenagers also frequently report loneliness as a feeling of emptiness, boredom, isolation, and an inability to fit in with their peers or develop interpersonal relationships. When they are rejected, alone, and unable to participate in their environment, they frequently experience loneliness. This demonstrates how their diverse life experiences may be connected to loneliness. There are several things that contribute to loneliness. Age, gender, sleeplessness, suicidal tendencies, smoking, alcohol use, and depressive and anxious sentiments have all been documented as contributing factors at the individual level. The likelihood of loneliness has been linked to interpersonal factors such as flawed peer relationships (victimization, handful of close friends, poor friendships), poor parental relationships (conflicting parental behavior, lack of parental warmth and affection, conflicts with parents), bullying experiences, and higher maternal education. Knowing about these variables and minimizing the changeable ones may help reduce the risk given that loneliness may raise the possibility of unanticipated mental and emotional conduct among female teenagers. (Marthoenis, 2022)

Our developing sense of self, or learning who we are, is a part of adolescence and early adulthood that affects our interactions. This frequently entails experimenting with new things and changing one's values, beliefs, and aesthetics. When your friends are going through the same thing as you but may not want to take the same route, it can be difficult. Maybe you discover that your ideals do not align, or maybe you don't feel like your previous friends accept you. You could experience bullying in some situations if you don't fit in. That can be problematic, especially for those who belong to groups that are stigmatized because of their race or ethnicity, sexual orientation, gender, or ability, or who already struggle with mental health issues.

Considering the relationship of loneliness to other indicators of social integration in earlier life course phases, there is a paucity of knowledge concerning the possible psychological effects of loneliness. By incorporating a life course approach, our study adds to the body of research on loneliness by examining demographic changes between early and late adolescence in terms of age, sex, and other factors, as well as the prevalence of loneliness and identifying the coping mechanisms used by them.

Statement of Problem

Loneliness prevailing among adolescents is an issue of concern. How do they deal with it, survive, and cope with it? What strategies do they use? Is there any gender difference?

Objectives of the study

- To provide data on the prevalence of loneliness among adolescents.
- To explore age, sex, and other demographic differences in loneliness from early to late adolescence.
- To identify coping strategies used to cope with loneliness.

Review Literature

Statistics show that loneliness is becoming more common, particularly among younger generations. According to a 2019 survey, 25% of people between the ages of 18 and 27 reported having no close friends. Another 22% claimed to have no friends at all (Ballard, 2019). Loneliness is most prevalent during adolescence; by the age of 18, more than 70% of teenagers report ongoing loneliness (Goosby et al., 2013). According to studies (Cacioppo & Cacioppo, 2018), loneliness is correlated with depression, introversion, a lack of social skills, and social isolation. During this developmental stage, adolescents also turn from using their parents as their primary socializing agents to using their peers (Crosnoe, 2000). Parental support and school involvement, especially for adolescents, may be crucial coping mechanisms for physical and mental health at a developmental stage when discomfort is common (Resnick et al., 1997; Giordano, 2003). The importance of social relationships to long-term health (Umberson and Montez, 2010).

Research Methodology

The study has a mixed research design with an exploratory orientation. The convenience sampling method was used in the study, through which a sample of 100 school students (50 boys and 50 girls) studying in the 12th grade (average age of 15.21 years) and 100 college students (50 males and 50 females) studying in the B.A. program (average age of 19.84 years) were selected.

Method participants: a sample of 100 school students (50 boys and 50 girls) studying in the 12th grade, with an average age of 15.21 years, and 100 college students 50 males and 50 females studying in the B.A. (average age: 19.84 years) were the participants of the study. Within each group, an equal number of boys and girls were selected. The population was primarily middle class, and the majority of adolescents (96%) lived with both parents. The sample was limited to subjects who were available to participate in the study, thus limiting the assumption of randomization. Furthermore, the subjects included in this study were also required to show: 1) no evidence of drug addiction or alcoholism; and 2) not be currently in treatment for diagnosed psychiatric illnesses.

Measures: Revised UCLA Loneliness Scale (Russell, D., Peplau, L.A., Cutrona, C.E., 1980) This is a 20-item scale to measure loneliness. The subjects were asked to indicate on a 4-point scale (ranging from "often" to "never") how often each statement is descriptive of themselves. Russell et al. (1980) and Perlman and Peplau (1981) reported good reliability (Cronbach alpha >.9) and evidence of validity for the revised UCLA loneliness scale in the Indian setup. Upmanyu, Upmanyu, and Dhingra (1992a, b) also found evidence for adequate psychometric characteristics of the revised UCLA loneliness scale when administered to adolescents. In the current study, the coefficient of alpha was found to be 0.93. Higher scores were self-descriptive, indicating a high level of loneliness.

Proforma: Subjects were also asked to provide information regarding demographic data such as sex, age, the ordinal position in the family, number of siblings, number of close friends, caste, and religiosity. Following Medora and Woodward (1986), religiosity was defined in terms of the frequency of attendance at a place of worship. Individuals who went to a place of worship a) more than once a week, b) more than once a week, or c) once every two weeks were classified as religious. On the other hand, people who went to a place of worship less often, for example, a) once a month, b) once every 6 months, c) once a year, or never, were classified as non-religious.

Consequently, no existing questionnaires were used, and no new ones were developed. The goal was to examine how individuals would respond to the instruction to "describe your loneliness experience" and how they would describe their coping strategies.

Results and Discussion

The first analysis was concerned with the prevalence of loneliness among boys and girls adolescents. The loneliness scores of male and female adolescents ranged from 22 to 62 (mean = 40.17, SD = 4.18), and 25 to 68 (mean = 48.18, SD = 5.07), respectively. According to a cut-off score ($M + 1\text{ SD}$), 16% and 10% of female and male adolescents, respectively, experience loneliness. As a result, a 2*2 (age by sex) ANOVA-analysis of variance revealed that the main effects for both sexes, $F(1,196) = 1.08$, and age, $F(1,196) = 1.41$, were non-significant in this study. Surprisingly, there was a significant interaction between gender and age ($F = 5.89, p < .05$). Females ($M=47.30$) were lonelier than males ($M=41.7$) during early adolescence, while males ($M=44.51$) were lonelier than females ($M=39.90$) during late adolescence. Further, the application of one-way analysis of variance, separately for 2 age levels, to study the influence of family rank, number of siblings, number of close friends, caste, and religiosity on the intensity of loneliness revealed no association between the intensity of loneliness and any of their demographic variables.

Another major concern in this study was the coping strategies used by adolescents to cope with loneliness during periods of loneliness. The strategies most frequently employed are presented in the table.

Table No.1: Percentage of Coping Strategies Employed by Early and Late Adolescents

Strategies	Early Adolescents (%)		Late Adolescents (%)	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
Watch Television	40	60	34	58
Read/Study	20	30	18	40
Engaging in Cooking/Household Work		20	2	36
Shopping		10		18
Exercise/Walk/Yoga	18		20	2
Religious Activities		6	2	20
Ignore Sleep	8	6		8
Smoking			4	

It appears that a vast majority of adolescents, regardless of the stage of adolescence and sex, report engaging in solitary activities to cope with loneliness. Although solitary involvement reflects a variety of activities and events, they are clearly not those activities that might help the person have a positive, pleasant experience that is conducive to replenishing one's energy and resources and that affords one the time and space to reflect, be creative, or just enjoy rest.

The study set out to achieve three objectives: a) to provide data on the prevalence of loneliness among Indian adolescents; b) to explore age, sex, and other demographic differences in loneliness from early through late adolescence; and c) to identify coping strategies being used to cope with loneliness.

The first objective findings from the present study indicated that the majority of adolescents, regardless of age and sex, experienced a moderate degree of loneliness. This result does not diminish the importance of adolescent loneliness; a considerable number of early as well as late adolescents did manifest acute loneliness, which is a terrorizing pain and an agonizing and frightening experience that leaves a person vulnerable, shaken, and often wounded and depressed.

Further, the expectations regarding the effect of age and sex differences on adolescent loneliness have not been confirmed. The data, however, seems to present a significant sex-by-age interaction. Thus, from the viewpoint of adolescent loneliness, what is new here is the finding that there is a reversal of sex differences in loneliness between early and late adolescence. Females scored markedly higher on loneliness during early adolescence, and males experienced more loneliness during late adolescence. This result seems to represent a serious threat to the viability of studying sex differences in loneliness without giving due consideration to the stage of adolescence. It is possible that pubertal change is likely to have a different meaning for boys and girls. Several studies have found that puberty usually has a positive meaning for boys because it makes them bigger and stronger, whereas pubertal change typically has some negative aspects for girls.

Based on these findings, it can be concluded that menstruating girls experience an odd state of self-ease in their own bodies across the whole of early adolescence. Additionally, because they lack sex education and pubertal transition counseling, they experience a painful detachment that serves as the basis for loneliness for a while. The study shows that, in certain circumstances, there is still a demand for and value placed on parental attention.

Young people frequently indicate that they feel the most alone at school, whereas family is a reassuring place. However, problems at home—such as disagreements or conflicts with family, the departure of a family member who was a source of support, or problems with family members' mental health or drug abuse—can make people feel more isolated. When people try to communicate with their parents about their loneliness, they sometimes report feeling rejected.

Strong, unpleasant emotions like anxiety, worry, sadness, or rage are common struggles for adolescents with mental health issues. In order to help people live better lives and have better connections with others, mental health therapy frequently focuses on imparting a set of skills to clearly evaluate, express, and manage their emotions.

The majority of people experience loneliness occasionally; it is transient and will pass once they are reconnected. But for other people, loneliness can persist for a long time and negatively affect their health. The stigma attached to chronic loneliness is one factor that keeps individuals there. Because those who suffer from loneliness are frequently perceived negatively—as introverted, pessimistic, or socially awkward—people do not want to be connected with them. Because loneliness is generally assumed to be about social exclusion, or a lack of touch with other people, someone who is accompanied by others might not understand that they should be classified as lonely. They could judge themselves for feeling lonely, which keeps them from reaching out for assistance.

Adolescence is a time of development during which the dynamics of interpersonal interactions alter. For instance, the purpose of friendship shifts from being one of friendship in childhood to one of emotional comfort and support in adolescence; at the same time, adolescents seek independence from the parents who first gave them that emotional support. Because of this, adolescents want more intimacy from their connections than they did as children and must balance these demands with their own identity discoveries. This means that adolescents must combine their requirements for emotional support with evolving attitudes and ideas that can be at odds with those of their childhood companions. Accordingly, early adolescence is marked by a significant degree of friendship instability. (Verity et al., 2022)

The ability to understand, express, and regulate our emotions is one of the most important skills we learn in life. For many, it's a lifelong journey. Since loneliness is a complicated emotion, it may be difficult to pinpoint a single cause for it and thus find a single remedy to make it go away. One person's solution

might not be the ideal solution for another. Don't lose faith if you experience loneliness and it seems like nothing is making a difference; it's possible that you haven't yet discovered the approach that works for you. Here are some suggestions for both males and females to prevent and overcome loneliness through emotional empowerment:

- Think about participating in community service or another enjoyable activity. These circumstances offer wonderful chances to socialise, make new acquaintances, and engage in new activities.
- Aim for the best. Instead of expecting rejection, as lonely individuals frequently do, try to concentrate on having good attitudes and thoughts in your social interactions.
- Concentrate on creating high-caliber connections or relationships. Look for individuals that are like-minded in terms of attitudes, hobbies, and ideals.
- Realize that feeling lonely is an indication that something has to be changed. Expecting things to change overnight is unrealistic, but you can start making changes now that will lessen your loneliness and help you form relationships that promote your well-being.
- Knowing how loneliness affects your life will help. Loneliness has negative psychological and physical effects. Make an effort to counteract them if you notice that some of these symptoms are having an impact on your mood.
- Start your own group or join one that already exists. For instance, you might attempt to start a Meetup group where locals with comparable interests can congregate. Additionally, you can think about joining a reading club, enrolling in a community college course, or enrolling in a fitness class.
- Enhance an existing relationship. In addition to making new friends, strengthening your current ties can also be a very effective approach to dealing with loneliness. Call a friend or member of your family that you haven't spoken to in a long.
- Speak to a reliable person. It's crucial to chat with someone in your life about how you are feeling. This could be a friend or family member, however, you may also think about speaking with your physician or a counselor. You can get in touch with a therapist whenever it's convenient for you, thanks to online counseling, which might be a fantastic option.
- A small group of close friends can prevent loneliness and lessen the detrimental effects on one's health that come with it. Having genuine face-to-face interactions with friends might improve one's sense of well-being.
- Accept the advantages of solitude. Numerous fun things we may do by ourselves when we're alone, like taking a stroll, reading, listening to music, or taking up a hobby, can make us feel good about ourselves while keeping our emotions at bay. Instead of lingering on negative ideas and prolonging or amplifying those sentiments, you are better equipped to let the sentiments pass when you divert your attention from how you experience when you're alone. Other advantages of solitude exist as well. It can allow you the space to recharge and reflect on life's events, especially if you spend a lot of time around people at work or school.

Conclusion

Adolescents need to have a healthy balance of sentiments and emotions in their brains and minds in order to be totally independent. Our study revealed significant gender differences in loneliness, which highlights the need for further research into the factors that influence and impact the emotion of loneliness in males and females. It might be distinct for them. Our investigation uncovered evidence of the coping mechanisms that young people adopt throughout this critical life stage, which is marked by fast developmental changes. Given these important formative years course findings, it is hoped that this research would prompt academics to think more seriously about loneliness as a social-psychological emotion that demands consideration at an earlier developmental stage. Due to the detrimental effects of

loneliness throughout the early life course and the coping mechanisms these adolescents are employing, they become more isolated.

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